

Students' understanding of physical culture and sports as a factor of health protection

Taras Bondar
Iryna Holoviichuk

University of Customs and Finance, Dnipro, Ukraine

Purpose: determination of the state of the relationship between students' knowledge on the factors of maintaining human health and the real state of their physical culture and sports activities.

Material & Methods: students from the specialties "Finance", "Banking and Insurance", "Economics", "Accounting and Taxation", "Management", "Psychology", "Law" took part in a sociological study.

Results: in the process of analyzing the survey data it was found that on the one hand, most students are aware of the factors of maintaining health and the benefits of physical activity to strengthen it. On the other hand, only a small part of students consciously use physical exercises to strengthen their own body.

Conclusions: the results obtained during the study showed that there is a need to improve pedagogical and organizational and managerial work on physical culture and sports leisure for children and youth, in particular, their involvement in modern forms of outdoor activities.

Keywords: physical education, health, students, physical activity, organization, management.

Introduction

The state order for the education of a healthy young generation is formulated in a number of normative acts, namely: the Constitution of Ukraine, the laws of Ukraine "On Education", "On Higher Education", "On Physical Culture and Sport". In particular, the Law of Ukraine "On Education" [2] and the Family Code of Ukraine [8], the responsibility for maintaining the health of the younger generation and young people by society lies with family members and educational institutions at all levels. Therefore, the capabilities of these social institutions to organize the physical activity of children and youth as the most effective way to strengthen their health, as well as the formation of their physical culture as an indispensable condition for a healthy lifestyle, are of particular importance.

The results of the analysis of scientific and methodological sources indicate the presence of a large number of studies on the physical education of youth. Important in the context of our study is the methodological foundations of pedagogical theory, scientific approaches to physical education as a leading component of a healthy lifestyle, the formation of a value-based attitude of the younger generation towards their own health (L. Ivanova [3], T. Krutsevich [4; 5], B. Shiyan [11]). A number of modern scientific studies are devoted to highlighting certain provisions of physical education as an important component of the educational process (Yu. Vaskov [1], V. Lozova [6], G. Trotsko [6]).

From our point of view, the conclusions of the research of L. Lubyshev [7], V. Sutula [9; 10] regarding the mechanisms of formation of the physical culture of a person's personality. These authors noted that the active participation of a person in physical education and sports is based on the existing need for a variety of physical activity.

At the same time, in the scientific literature there are no ways

to overcome the contradiction between the importance of physical activity in the process of formation and strengthening of youth's health and the low level of organizational and managerial work to attract students to physical education and the latest forms of organization of recreational and recreational activities, especially outside academic work.

Therefore, there is a need to clarify the relationship between students' knowledge regarding the factors of maintaining human health and the real state of their physical culture and sports activities, which determines the **purpose of this study**.

Material and Methods of the research

In May 2019, the authors conducted a sociological study among students of 1–4 years of the University of Customs and Finance of 6 specialties in health protection and the organization of their leisure. During the survey, a closed questionnaire was used. The results are summarized in table. In total, 599 future specialists in the field of economics, finance, law and psychology took part in the survey. The sampling error is 2,5% with 95% reliability of the survey results.

Results of the research

From the analysis presented in table. 1 of the materials it follows that the vast majority of students (88.1%) consider it important to maintain health. In the context of faculties, we note that the low percentage of students (80.7%) who think so are students in the specialty "Psychology", and the highest (92.2%) – in the direction "Economics". At the same time, the students surveyed have the opinion that the most important factor in maintaining health is the absence of bad habits in a person (38.2%), then (in importance) – a healthy and rational diet, an optimal regime of physical activity, an optimal mode of training and rest, active leisure in recreational areas. However,

Students' Attitudes to Health Factors

Survey directions	Finance, Banking and Insurance n=100	Economics n=98	Accounting and Taxation n=101	Management n=103	Psychology n=97	Law n=100	Averages n=599
<i>Most important factors maintaining health</i>							
Healthy eating	33,1	28,2	35,8	29,1	29,6	26,9	30,5
Mode of work (study) and rest	30,1	28,2	29,5	41,7	27,4	18,8	29,3
Optimal physical activity	36,2	20,9	30,6	27,2	22,4	43,8	30,2
Lack of bad habits;	37,7	41,8	39,3	35	30	45,6	38,2
Outdoor activities in recreational areas	23,1	12,7	16,8	8,7	15,2	15	15,3
<i>Determine the importance of health</i>	86,2	90,9	87,9	92,2	80,7	90,6	88,1
<i>Student leisure</i>							
Friends	61,5	46,4	60,1	57,3	38,1	56,3	53,3
Entertainment facilities (disco, club, cafe, etc.)	27,7	17,3	24,9	23,3	23,8	19,4	22,7
The television	16,9	17,3	16,8	11,7	15,7	16,3	15,8
Internet	24,6	26,4	30,1	32	15,3	23,8	25,4
Computer games	6,2	2,7	9,2	4,9	6,7	8,8	6,4
Sports facilities (sports section, fitness club, pool, water park, dance groups, etc.)	13,1	16,4	15,6	22,3	14,8	34,4	19,4
<i>Lack of bad habits</i>	71,5	66,4	53,2	60,2	49,8	67,5	61,4
<i>Bad habits</i>							
Smoking	5,4	11,8	21,4	16,5	20,2	14,4	15
Alcohol use (low alcohol drinks, beer)	10	10,9	23,7	16,5	19,7	18,1	16,5
Alcohol consumption (strong alcoholic drinks - vodka, cognac)	1,5	3,6	4	9,7	3,1	2,5	4,1
Alcohol consumption (alcoholic beverages - wine, champagne)	8,5	9	19,7	9,7	11,2	7,5	10,9
<i>Those wishing to participate in physically active leisure</i>	81,5	86,4	78,3	76,7	69,5	93,8	81
<i>Participation in sports activities</i>							
Professional sports activities	1,5	9	3,5	1	2,2	21,3	6,4
Visit to the sports section	10,8	16,4	6,9	9,7	12,1	34,4	15,1
Exclusively in the physical education classes of universities	73,8	44,5	62,4	51,5	48	30,6	51,8
A visit to the gym on the territory of the university	3,9	6,4	4	2,9	4,9	11,3	5,6
A visit to the gym or sports section outside universities	10	12,7	8,1	14,6	10,8	22,5	13,1
Do not participate in physical education sports	14,6	14,5	16,2	27,2	16,6	3,1	15,4
<i>Most significant motivational factors for students to conduct physical education classes</i>							
Evaluation	35,4	33,6	29,5	26,2	30,9	20	29,3
Lesson content	9,2	10	13,9	24,3	12,1	23,1	15,4
Result of testing the development of physical qualities	6,2	2,7	5,8	29,1	4,9	12,5	10,2
desire to move	20,8	17,3	18,5	21,4	14,8	30,6	20,6
Desire for emotional satisfaction	28,5	20	42,8	27,2	23,8	23,1	27,6
Positive effects of physical activity on one's own health	38,5	30,9	27,8	35,9	24,2	46,9	34
<i>Motivational factors for physical exercise in their free time</i>							
Desire to be healthy (including deprivation of a chronic disease)	43,1	36,4	49,1	39,8	30	49,4	41,3
Desire to have a beautiful (athletic) physique	57,7	39,1	47,4	49,5	36,3	38,8	44,8
Financial motives	7,7	0,9	5,8	-	3,1	8,8	5,3
Desire to see the world	7,7	5,5	5,8	4,6	6,3	13,8	7,3
It's fashionable	1,5	3,6	6,9	-	5,4	3,8	4,2
Desire to assert oneself among peers	4,6	1,8	2,3	1	2,2	6,9	3,1
Forced parents or educators (including training)	2,3	6,4	3,5	4,9	5,8	1,3	4
Desire to improve your body	29,2	27,3	27,2	42,7	29,6	42,5	33,1
<i>Reasons that interfere with physically active leisure</i>							
Not enough time	81,5	74,6	74,6	65	58,7	55,6	68,3
Believe that sport is a futile exercise	0,8	1,8	2,3	1	1,8	0,6	1,4
The lack of conditions in universities for sports	8,5	8,2	6,9	4,9	9,4	16,9	9,1
Lack of information about where in the university you can play sports	6,2	9	8	12,6	10,3	13,1	9,9
<i>Participate in the university's public sports</i>	20,8	15,5	38,2	30,1	22	50,6	29,5
<i>Those wishing to participate in the public sports life of the university</i>	30	14,6	39,9	14,6	25,1	61,9	31

despite the prevailing opinion among students that one of the main factors in maintaining human health is the absence of bad habits, only 61.4% (on average) do not have them. At the same time, 15% of students smoke, 16.5% drink low-alcohol drinks, and 10.4% drink wine.

For almost all the students surveyed (except for the specialties "Accounting and Taxation" and "Law"), such an important factor in strengthening human health and preventing disease, as physical activity, is not significant. This is evidenced by the results of a further analysis of the sociological survey. So, students spend leisure time in communication with friends (53.3%), instead of classes in sports clubs, fitness clubs, swimming pools, dance groups, pools and water parks.

Only 19.4% of students organize their active leisure, and thus put spending their free time only in fourth place, and students in the specialties "Finance, Banking and Insurance" and "Psychology" generally rank fifth in their priorities, respectively 13.1%, 16.4%, 15.6%, 14.8%, and only future jurists – in the second (34.4%). The vast majority (68.3%) of students are justified by the fact that they do not have time for physical education and sports. Moreover, most of these students study in the specialties "Finance, banking and insurance" – 81.5%, "Economics" – 74.6%, "Accounting and taxation" – 74.6%. Therefore, for the majority of students (51.8%) physical education classes during school hours is the only way to organize motor activity. Most of these students are in the specialties "Finance, Banking and Insurance" (73.8%) and "Accounting and Taxation" (62.4%), the smallest – "Law" (30.6%).

The most significant motivating factors regarding attending physical education classes for future financiers, economists, lawyers and psychologists indicate an understanding of the positive impact of physical exercises on their own health (average 34%), the ability to get a positive assessment (average 29.3%), and the opportunity to get emotional satisfaction from classes (on average 27,6%).

Further analysis of the materials of the sociological survey confirmed this contradiction. So, the main motives that prompt extracurricular activities in physical exercises (recreational and health-improving activities) and sports, respondents indicated a desire to have a good figure (44.8%), health (41.3%) and a desire to improve the condition of the body (33.1%). Other answers are not significant. Moreover, this trend is characteristic of most areas of specialist training, except for the specialties "Accounting and Taxation" and "Law". Students of these specialties are the most important factor in motivation

for physical exercises and sports outside the classroom, consider the positive impact of such classes on human health, in accordance with 49.1% and 49.4%.

So, there is a contradiction – on the one hand, most students are aware of the benefits of physical exercise to maintain health, and on the other hand, only a small part of them voluntarily uses to strengthen their own body. This may be due both to the content of curricula for the formation of a worldview and an active attitude towards physical education at all levels of education, and to the imperfection of the management of physical culture and sports work with the population.

There is a contradiction, which is also confirmed by students' responses to participation in the self-government of physical education and sports activities in an educational institution. So, on average, only 29.5% of respondents participate in various social activities (student council commissions, refereeing, organizing and conducting competitions, the work of a sports club, etc.) related to physical education. Most of these students are students in the specialties of "Accounting and Taxation" (38.2%) and "Law" (50.6%), the least – "Economics" (15.5%) and "Management" (22%). A similar situation has developed with regard to students' desire to participate in such social activities – an average of only 31%. Most of all those wishing to take part in it also study in the specialties "Accounting and Taxation" (39.9%) and "Law" (61.9%).

Conclusions / Discussion

The results of a sociological study showed that among students, to a certain extent, health and safety competencies were not formed. In particular, in the presence of theoretical knowledge, the motivation of students for active physical education and sports and active participation in social activities in the health field is at a low level.

Most students do not associate their leisure time with physical exercises, although the modern market of recreational and recreational services has a wide selection of forms of outdoor activities, have the main signs of fitness, and sometimes sports activities.

The results obtained suggest either the imperfection of the curriculum for secondary and higher schools, or the insufficient level of organizational and managerial work on the physical culture and sports leisure of children and youth. Therefore, there is a need for further research in this direction, which determines the **prospects for future research**.

Conflict of interests. The authors declare that no conflict of interest.
Financing sources. This article didn't get the financial support from the state, public or commercial organization.

References

1. Vaskov, Yu.V. (2013), *Teoretychni i metodychni zasady navchannia fizychnoi kultury uchniv osnovnoi shkoly: avtoref. dys. d-ra ped. nauk* [Theoretical and methodological foundations of physical education teaching of primary school students: Dr. of Sciences thesis abstract], Nat. ped. them. M.P. Dragomanov, Kyiv. (in Ukr.)
2. VRU (2017), Law of Ukraine "On Education", available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2145-19>. (in Ukr.)
3. Ivanova, L.I. & Omelchuk, OV (2018), "Separate issues of optimization of the legal framework for improving the efficiency of physical education of students", *Naukovyi chasopys Natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu imeni M. P. Drahomanova. Seriya 15 : Naukovo-pedahohichni problemy fizychnoi kultury (fizychna kultura i sport)*, Iss. 3K (97), pp. 228-231. (in Ukr.)
4. Kutsevich, T. (2008), *Teoriia i metodyka fizychnoho vykhovannia* [Theory and Methods of Physical Education], Vol.2, Olympic Literature, Kiev. (in Ukr.)
5. Kutsevich, T. (2012), "On the Effectiveness of the Physical Education System in Secondary Schools of Ukraine", *Sportyvnyi visnyk Prydniprovshchyny*, No. 1, pp. 10-15.

provia, No. 1, pp. 239-243. (in Russ.)

6. Lozova, V.I. & Trotsko, G.V. (2002), *Teoretychni osnovy navchannia i vykhovannia* [Theoretical Foundations of Learning and Education], OVC, Kharkiv. (in Ukr.)

7. Lubyshcheva, L.I. (2016), *Sotsyolohyia fizycheskoi kultury i sporta* [Sociology of Physical Education and Sport], Academia, Moscow. (in Russ.)

8. VRU (2002), The Family Code of Ukraine (2002), available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2947-14>. (in Ukr.)

9. Sutula, V.O. (2012), *Teoretyko-metodychni zasady formuvannia fizychnoi kultury osobystosti v umovakh tsilisnoi sotsialno-pedahohichnoi systemy: dys. ... d-ra ped. nauk* [Theoretical and methodological foundations of formation of physical culture of personality in the conditions of holistic social-pedagogical system: Dr. of Sciences diss.], Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture, Kharkiv. (in Ukr.)

10. Sutula, V., Shuteev, V., Lutsenko, L., Kolisnichenko, A., Ispravnikov, V., Deyneko, A. & Bodrenkova, I. (2017), "Features of the influence of sports on the personality of students", *Slobozhans'kij naukovo-sportivnij visnik*, No. 1 (57), pp. 100-105. (in Ukr.)

11. Shiyan, B.M. & Papusha, V.G. (2000), *Teoriia fizychnoho vykhovannia* [Theory of physical education], Zbruch, Ternopil. (in Ukr.)

Received: 19.07.2019.

Published: 31.08.2019.

Information about the Authors

Taras Bondar: *PhD (Physical Education and Sport); University of Customs and Finance: 2/4 Volodymyr Vernadsky Street, Dnipro, Dnepropetrovsk Region, 49000, Ukraine.*

ORCID.ORG/0000-0002-1389-6614

E-mail: tsbondar@gmail.com

Iryna Holoviichuk: *PhD (Physical Education and Sport); University of Customs and Finance: 2/4 Volodymyr Vernadsky Street, Dnipro, Dnepropetrovsk Region, 49000, Ukraine.*

ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-9259-8203

E-mail: irinaucf@gmail.com